

PARTICIPATORY MAPPING WITH INDIGENOUS COMMUNITIES IN THE LOS FLAMENCOS NATURAL PARK AND FAUNA AND FLORA SANCTUARY, ON THE NORTHERN COAST OF COLOMBIA.

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Abstract.

This study corresponds to a participatory mapping activity carried out within the project "Assessment of environmental quality by microplastics in the Santuario de Fauna y Flora los Flamencos (SFFF)," located in the village of Camarones, jurisdiction of the Special, Tourist, and Cultural District of Riohacha, La Guajira, Colombia. This activity involved the participation of ethnic communities living within the SFFF protected area. The primary objective of participatory mapping was to identify points of interest or sources of pollution relevant to the project's development through the use of printed maps of the study area. During the mapping activity, four maps were created, locating 75 areas of interest, 3 oral histories and 13 Cachirra events, that refers to the death of fish caused by changes in climatic variables, such as increased water temperature and salinity, as well as decreased dissolved oxygen, a direct consequence of evaporation. This phenomenon occurs most frequently during the summer season and affects species that constitute a traditional food source for the

communities. Additionally, undocumented routes for waste transport to the lagoon were identified. This methodology provides primary information with the exact location

of points of interest to identify critical areas linked to microplastics, which raised awareness and generated community consciousness, and the integration of sites of collective memory.

Keywords: Participatory mapping, SFFF, microplastics, solid waste.

Introduction.

Global plastic production has reached alarming levels, reaching 413.8 million tons in 2024 (Plastics Europe, 2024). This material, omnipresent in daily life, has become one of the main pollutants of coastal marine ecosystems, representing more than 80% of the waste (Machado Menezes et al., 2025). This plastic waste in the environment can degrade into small particles through ultraviolet radiation, the action of water currents, and physical-mechanical degradation. When it reaches a size between 1µm and 5mm, it is classified as secondary microplastics (MPs) (Ekawati

et al., 2024); However, they can also be intentionally manufactured in industrial, cosmetic, and household products, called primary MPs. MPs can cause physical and chemical impacts on living beings, causing bioaccumulation in their organs, physical damage to their gastrointestinal tract (which prevents proper feeding), and chemical damage due to the toxic effects of persistent pollutants, which can be carcinogenic and cause endocrine disruption. They can also affect humans by transferring toxic substances across trophic levels due to their hydrophobic properties ("Plastic Peril: Unraveling Microplastics Threats to Health and Ecosystems," 2024).

Participatory mapping is an important tool that helps communities to visualize their connection with their territory and the socio-environmental issues that are present in the area where they live, as well as highlighting historical and cultural knowledge (Corbett, J.,2009). In the context of the SFFF, this tool takes on special significance due to the coexistence of Wayuu indigenous communities and Afro-descendant communities in a protected area with a diverse ecosystem of great ecological importance, consisting of mangroves, forests, beaches, lagoons, and a variety of fauna and flora species (Moreno-M & Acuña-Vargas, 2015), which are affected by plastic pollution. This approach allows for the identification of the sociocultural and ecological values attributed to a specific area, which is essential for the management of the protected area (Molina-Urruela et al., 2024).

Methodology.

The mapping was carried out with the participation of traditional indigenous

authorities, Afro-descendant leaders, members of communities living within the SFFF, support from operators of Colombia's National Natural Parks, the interdisciplinary team from the La Universidad de La Guajira, and members of the Heidelberg Institute for Geographic Information Technology (HeiGIT) and the Urban Big Data Centre (UBDC) – University of Glasgow. This activity involved the participation of a member who speaks Wayuunaiki, which is essential for this type of community activity. The activity used printed maps of the area (satellite view and street view) from Open Street Map, green, red, black, and blue markers, pencils, and pens.

As part of the methodology, three phases were proposed: In the first phase, the activity was presented to the participants (community leaders, traditional authorities, and fishermen).

In addition, the informed consent form was read to them in Spanish and Wayuunaiki. In the second phase, key concepts about social mapping and the tools to be used were explained to them, and they were shown various photographs of the territory where they had the task of identifying flood zones, places of cultural importance, among others. During the third phase, participants were provided with satellite images taken with the Sketch Map Tool, a software tool developed by HeiGIT for creating schematic maps by collecting, digitizing and georeferencing local spatial knowledge (Sketch Map Tool, 2023). These images showed everyday landmarks to the communities, such as the entrance to the lagoon and the park shack. Then, participants were randomly divided into three groups, where, through guided

conversations, they were asked to identify points of importance such as areas of solid waste accumulation, sewage discharges, river or stream inflows to the Navío Quebrado lagoon, areas of increased fishing activity, among others. Following the world café methodology, the maps were rotated among the discussion groups approximately every 20 minutes. This dynamic allowed participants from different groups to engage with each map, contributing diverse perspectives and insights. As a result, a broader range of points was covered, enriching the collective understanding and fostering inclusive dialogue across all participants. In addition to these three maps, a fourth was set aside to mark points of cultural importance or with a story that had been recounted by the participants, which was displayed on a table

by one of the team members. Finally, the data obtained in the SFFF was transferred to the QGIS program, and all the maps were digitized.

Results.

Based on the activity carried out with community members, a total of four maps were produced identifying different points of interest for the project, such as areas of wastewater discharge and solid waste accumulation shown on the figure 1, which are closely related to the problem of microplastics, the participants implied that responsibility for this problem is not only the responsibility of tourists and occasional visitors, but also their own, as they are the ones who carry out their daily activities in the area. On another note, in the cultural context, some holy sites were identified,

Figure 1: Solid waste accumulation.

Source: Project results.

such as the named "cabeza de burro," which is an area where the spirit of a headless horseman ("Chaneta" in wayunnaiki) used to torment them, for that, the community members decided to place a donkey's head in that spot, managing to scare the spirit away. In the same order of ideas, the points of interest identified are mentioned in table 1.

Table 1: Points of interest.

Point of interest	Quantity
Holy areas	19
Solid waste accumulation	14
Cachirra event	13
Sedimentation areas	10
Fishing areas	10
Fishing communities	10
Waste water inlets	5
Solid waste flow	4
Continental water inlets	3
Storytelling points	3

Source: Project results.

In addition, undocumented routes for solid waste being carried into the lagoon were identified, which must be addressed as a matter of priority.

Conclusions.

The participatory mapping methodology used in the SFFF proved to be a useful strategy for identifying critical areas of wastewater discharge, solid waste accumulation, and areas of high fishing activity, among others, as first-hand data was obtained through the experiences and observations of community members in the protected area.

In the same way, the mapping process helped the community recognize its role in generating MPs and integrated elements of collective memory and holy sites such as "Cabeza de burro" into the cartography,

reinforcing the link between environmental management and cultural heritage.

On the other hand, the digitization of the resulting maps constitutes a solid basis for designing adaptive management strategies that integrate cleanup actions, continuous monitoring, and environmental education, which also help prevent and mitigate the environmental impacts caused to the ecosystem. Additionally, the data collected through this process contributes to larger academic and scientific analyses, providing valuable information for interdisciplinary research. These findings are being reviewed and refined for inclusion in future high-impact publications that seek to inform policy, guide conservation initiatives, and strengthen community environmental management.

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